

Schmidt Ocean Institute Post Expedition Report

Octopus Odyssey / Octopus Odyssey (Too)

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1 Overview

SOI Expedition ID	FKt230602	FKt231202
Vessel	R/V <i>Falkor (too)</i>	R/V <i>Falkor (too)</i>
Expedition Name	Octopus Odyssey	Octopus Odyssey (too)
Expedition Dates	2023/06/2 - 2023/06/21	2023/12/2 - 2023/12/15
Departure Port	Puntarenas, Costa Rica	Balboa, Panama
Termination Port	Puntarenas, Costa Rica	Golfoito, Costa Rica
Ocean	Pacific Ocean	Pacific Ocean

Map of Expedition Location

Figure 1: Map of FKt230602 (green lines) and FKt231202 (red lines) Expeditions Locations.

1.1 Expeditions Overview

The west coast of Costa Rica is home to numerous seamounts - underwater mountains that facilitate stunning biodiversity in the deep sea. While some of these seamounts have been explored, and a few are protected by the Costa Rican government, others have been minimally studied, especially along the northwestern edge of the Pacific Ocean Margin.

Through a two-part expedition, Octopus Odyssey and Octopus Odyssey (Too), a team of international scientists investigated the biodiversity of unprotected seamounts in this underexplored region. The primary target was the El Dorado Outcrop, which is one of Costa Rica’s “off-axis” seamounts on the complex Cocos Plate. It is part of a group of seamounts formed on the East Pacific Rise, as compared to more southerly seamounts offshore Costa Rica that were formed from the Cocos-Nazca Spreading Center.

An “Octopus Garden” was first discovered in the Dorado Outcrop in 2013. On this small outcrop, female octopuses brood their eggs together along low-temperature vents, a phenomenon that scientists had never seen before. Female octopuses were known to brood their eggs alone in rocky crevices, passing away after their eggs hatch.

The science team’s ultimate goal was to understand better the hydrogeology, microbiology, ecology, and geochemistry that may facilitate octopus nurseries while characterizing life-supporting services provided by the ecosystems on these seamounts. The first expedition took place in June 2023 and a second follow-on expedition took place in December 2023 to continue their research, collect experiments they placed earlier in the year, and examine new regions never-before-seen by humans.

1.2 Authorizations and Permitting

Permit Number	Permit Authority	Permit Focus
DGP 392-2023 DGP	Republica de Costa Rica	Marine Scientific Research
R-026-2023-OT-CONAGEBIO	CONAGEBIO	Access to biodiversity

1.3 Expeditions Timeline

The first expedition, Octopus Odyssey (FKt230602), departed from Puntarenas, Costa Rica, on June 1, 2023, and returned to Puntarenas, Costa Rica, on June 22, 2023.

The second expedition, Octopus Odyssey (Too) (FKt231202), began on December 2, 2023, departing from Balboa, Panama, and ended on December 15, 2023, in Golfito, Costa Rica.

1.4 Expeditions Objectives

The Octopus Odyssey expeditions’ objective was to search for more low-temperature hydrothermal vents on Costa Rica’s northwestern seamounts, documenting microbial and observable communities, and the relationships between them, on these lesser-explored geologic features. Through this work, the goal was to capture a complete picture of the ecosystem services provided by the seamounts. Specifically, the team aimed to: 1) Determine if octopuses are brooding viable eggs in the warm waters of hydrothermal vents found at the Dorado Outcrop in Costa Rican waters; and 2) Ascertain linkages between the microbes harnessing energy from the fluids and rocks surrounding them, other microbial processes, and animals inhabiting the seamounts in Costa Rican waters.

During the June expedition, the team deployed microbial colonization experiments and various types of animal shelters. The team returned in December to recover the experiments, which

were designed to improve understanding of the connections between the life present and the rocks and fluids surrounding these seafloor features.

2 Expeditions Accomplishments

2.1 At-sea Accomplishments

In June of 2023, an international team traveled to the region aboard R/V *Falkor (too)* with a major goal to determine if the eggs at the nursery were viable, as past expeditions to the outcrop had never seen evidence of developing embryos. From 2 - 21 June 2023, 14 dives with ROV *SuBastian* were conducted to explore six seafloor features (only one of which had ever been explored before), augmented by 13 full-water-column CTD Niskin Rosette casts and six multibeam surveys. Roughly 229 hours of ROV operations took place (172 hours on the seafloor + 57 hours of ascent/descent), resulting in 208 hours of video. The longest ROV dive was approximately 35 hours, and the deepest depth of the ROV exploration was 3178 m. There were 285 sampling events during the ROV dives: 150 primary biological specimens (plus associates), 66 sediment push cores, 28 ROV Niskin samples of bottom water, 13 squeezer fluid samples, and 30 rock samples were collected. The expedition also included deployments of 22 different experiments, which were recovered in December 2023, along with 2 experiments that were deployed on the Dorado Outcrop in 2014. 31 video transects were also conducted. On the first ROV dive at the nursery in June, a baby octopus hatching was witnessed by the ROV video cameras, confirming the primary hypothesis that there are viable octopus nurseries in this region. The fifth known octopus nursery in the world was also found, on a different seafloor feature 30 nautical miles away.

In December 2023, the team returned to this region on RV *Falkor (too)* to ask new questions about biodiversity in the region and to recover experiments to track the hydrogeology of the area. From 1 - 15 December 2023, the scientists conducted twelve full-ocean depth ROV dives with ROV *SuBastian*, augmented by five full-ocean depth CTD Niskin Rosette casts, and multibeam operations resulting in 7416 km² of coverage in Costa Rican waters. There were roughly 104 hours of ROV operations (55 hours on the seafloor + 49 hours of ascent/descent), resulting in approximately 141 hours of video. The longest ROV dive was a little over 16 hours, and the deepest depth of ROV exploration was 3179 mbsl. There were 241 sampling events with the ROV in the water: 93 primary biological specimens, 14 sediment push cores, 21 ROV Niskin samples, 20 rock samples, and 51 fluid samples collected with a third-party SUPR sampler were collected. On the ship, an additional 66 secondary associate biological samples from primary specimens were created, bringing the total number of samples to 307 (this does not include subsamples). 23 video transects were conducted. The biggest finding of the return expedition was confirmation that the octopus nurseries offshore Costa Rica support baby octopus throughout the year, not just during the summer rainy season.

Scientists onboard witnessed spectacular scenes of the first moments of life, as baby octopus emerged from their eggs, including the ROV following one hatchling for an epic journey over 150 m into the water column. Immature eggs were also observed to have tiny octopus embryos inside. Having two expeditions to the same region in one year was essential for confirming this finding.

Equally as important as achieving the scientific objectives was capacity sharing, early career development, and raising awareness of deep-sea heritage in Latin America. The international expedition teams gathered to achieve collaborative co-production of knowledge and training with Costa Ricans, honoring the work in Costa Rica's waters. Spanish-speaking scientists were given priority for dive lead watches to enable livestream narration in Spanish and priority for leadership experience. Ship-to-shore engagements were also prioritized for Spanish-speaking audiences, particularly in Costa Rica. These efforts were intended to raise the profile of the deep-sea heritage in Costa Rica ahead of the UN Ocean Conference meeting taking place in Costa Rica in June 2024 and in France in June 2025.

Over 300 biological specimens collected on the two expeditions are archived at the Museum of Zoology at the University of Costa Rica, enabling current and future generations of students and researchers to develop expertise in regional deep-sea animals. It is likely that many of the specimens collected represent new species and new records of known species for the region. Rock and sediment samples collected on the expeditions are revolutionizing the understanding of the complex geological origins and processes occurring on this part of the seafloor. Surprisingly, initial analysis of microfossils in sediments reveals that seafloor sediments are millions-of-years old, indicating strong currents, dissolution, and scouring. In addition, fossils of beaked whales were found on numerous outcrops. All microfossils and macrofossils are archived in the Paleontology collection at the Central American School of Geology at the University of Costa Rica for continued study, with additional mineralogical samples shared with the Global Marine Minerals Program at the U.S. Geological Society. Finally, bathymetric and subbottom profile mapping data gathered on the expeditions were used to define the diverse seafloor features in this region and to propose official names to GEBCO. The formal naming effort is being led by Costa Rican scientists in consultation with the Costa Rican Committee on Nomenclature; the new proposed names were unanimously approved by the committee and will now be included on Costa Rican maps.

2.1.1 Science

Three different types of low-temperature hydrothermal vents were detected during the expedition, each sustaining life. Fluid samples collected at these sites enabled the study of the microbiomes within the hydrothermal waters, which were used to understand the functions microbes perform and how they connect to the microbiomes of animals living in these places. The water samples collected have shown interconnectivity between features, which helps researchers understand the deep sea as a network of connected habitats rather than a series of isolated features.

Scientists confirmed that *Muusoctopus* nurseries offshore of Costa Rica support baby octopuses throughout the year, not just during the rainy season, as observed in June.

The observed deep-sea octopus and skate nurseries meet definitions of [Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems](#) and [Ecologically and Biologically Sensitive Areas](#) because they are essential for the survival of these octopus populations. These nutrient-rich ecosystems are home to species that are slow to recover from disturbance. The research from this expedition will aid in creating more effective conservation management plans for the country of Costa Rica.

2.1.2 Innovative Technologies

The Octopus Odyssey expeditions were the first to incorporate video imagery taxonomic annotation with the Tator software platform, a trial conducted in collaboration with Schmidt Ocean Institute. Outputs of the annotations have been, and will continue to be, uploaded to FathomNet to speed automated imagery analysis.

2.2 Post-expedition Activities and Accomplishments

2.2.1 Overview

Exploration of the six seafloor features on the expedition revealed an incredibly rich biodiversity and biogeography of life on ancient volcanoes offshore Costa Rica. The seamounts offshore Costa Rica support at least four new species of deep-sea octopuses, based on the collection of specimens from both Octopus Odyssey expeditions in June and December 2023. This is an unprecedented biodiversity of octopus in this small area, especially at these depths. Additional evidence of the hydrogeology of the region was also documented, such as how water moves in, out, and through oceanic crust. This data can inform why volcanoes and earthquakes in Costa Rica vary as different types of seamounts and oceanic crust subducts beneath overriding plates. Analyses of samples and data are still ongoing.

Imagery and specimens collected from the Octopus Odyssey expeditions have been used extensively in Costa Rica to raise awareness of Costa Rica's deep-sea heritage. Listed below are the dozens of public presentations and exhibitions that have taken place since the expeditions. These activities have raised the profile of Costa Rica's deep-sea heritage, leading to naming of seafloor features, use of information by national ministries for conservation and resource management, and influence of international policy making connected to the UN Ocean Conference.

2.2.2 New Discoveries

One of the discoveries may be a new species of *Muusoctopus*, the only type of octopus observed brooding its eggs on the low-temperature hydrothermal vents. This discovery supports the previous hypothesis that only the *Muusoctopus* genus has evolved to brood their eggs in warm springs on the seafloor.

2.2.3 Software Utilized

- [Tator](#)

2.3 Data

Datasets acquired during the two expeditions and those derived from the analysis of collected data and samples as of this report's publication date.

2.3.1 Available Datasets

Data Type	Curator
Vessel underway data	Octopus Odyssey: Rolling Deck to Repository Octopus Odyssey (too): Rolling Deck to Repository

Data Type	Curator
ADCP	Octopus Odyssey: University of Hawaii Data Acquisition System
	Octopus Odyssey (too): University of Hawaii Data Acquisition System
Processed Multibeam from <i>Falkor (too)</i> from Octopus Odyssey (too)	Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)
ROV <i>SuBastian</i> Sensor Data	Octopus Odyssey: Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS) Octopus Odyssey (too): Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)
ROV Image Data	Octopus Odyssey: Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS) Octopus Odyssey (too): Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)
ROV Event Log Data	Octopus Odyssey: Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS) Octopus Odyssey (too): Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)
Curated ROV dive logs & cruise reports	Zenodo, DOI 10.5281/zenodo.18266778
ROV sample metadata	BCO-DMO, https://www.bco-dmo.org/dataset/935534
ROV fluid sample cell count data	BCO-DMO, https://www.bco-dmo.org/dataset/964619

2.3.2 Pending Datasets (as of January 2026)

- ROV video imagery taxonomic annotation
- ROV biology specimen imagery and subsample records
- ROV rock and sediment sample imagery and subsample records
- ROV rock and sediment sample microbial genetic sequence data
- ROV heat flow sensor data
- ROV OsmoSampler sample chemical data
- Shipboard CTD Niskin cast water sample metadata
- Shipboard CTD Niskin water sample chemical data

2.4 Publications

Banks, S., Alonso, D., Vides, M., Yepes, V., Cortes, J., Naranjo-Elizondo, B., et al. (2025). Unveiling Hidden Dimensions of the Eastern Tropical Pacific Marine Conservation Corridor. *Journal of Ocean Technology*, 20 (2),

Cambronero-Solano, S., J. Cortés, B. Orcutt, D. Amon, O. Breedy, E.J. Cowell, T. D'Angelo, M. Droge, M. Guilhon, C. Hiller, R. Lauer, H. Lutz, W. Matamoros, B. Naranjo-Elizondo, R. Perrin, G. Ramírez, C. Sánchez-Noguera, M.I. Sandoval, J. Voight, S. Cortés & F. Vásquez. 2024. Costa Rica Desconocida: Un mar de oportunidades a través de la investigación del océano profundo. Revista Costarricense de Política Exterior, Edición Especial, Diplomacia Azul: Una mirada hacia el Océano: 30-51. [Journal of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Costa Rica](#)

3 Appendix

3.1 Science Parties Information

Scientist	Institution
Beth Orcutt	Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences
Jorge Cortés-Núñez	University Of Costa Rica
Amanda Sutherland	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Andrew Fisher	University of California, Santa Cruz
Beatriz Naranjo	University Of Costa Rica
Celeste Noguera	University Of Costa Rica
Celeste Sanchez	University Of Costa Rica
Diva Amon	SpeSeas
Emily Cowell	Temple University
Esteban Herrera	Costa Rican Government
Fiorella Vasquez	University Of Costa Rica
Geoff Wheat	University of Alaska Fairbanks
Gustavo Ramirez	California State University, Los Angeles
Holly Lutz	Field Museum of Natural History
Janet Voight	Field Museum of Natural History
Julie Huber	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Leonardo Chacon	University Of Costa Rica
Maila Guilhon	GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel
Manuel "Oscar" Almacen	California State University, Los Angeles
Maria Isabel Sandoval	University Of Costa Rica
Marino Protti	National University of Costa Rica
Miguel Semedo	CIIMAR - University of Porto
Nixon Lara Quesada	Costa Rican Institute of Fisheries and Aquaculture (INCOPECA)

Scientist	Institution
Odalisca Breedy Shadid	University Of Costa Rica
Rachel Lauer	University of Calgary
Randi Rotjan	Boston University
Rob Perrin	University of Calgary
Ryu Akiba	University of California, Santa Cruz
Sergio Cambroner	National University of Costa Rica
Tim D'Angelo	Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences
Valeria Naranjo	University Of Costa Rica
Wendolyn Matamoros Calderon	University Of Costa Rica

3.2 Conferences/Presentations/Posters

Cortés J, Orcutt B, and the Octopus Odyssey Science Parties. [Discovery of octopus nurseries at low-temperature hydrothermal vents on seamounts offshore Costa Rica](#). Ocean Sciences Meeting 2024. DS44A-0408. February 2024. New Orleans.

Droge M, Cortés J, Orcutt B, and the Octopus Odyssey Science Party. [Immersive art to tell the story of the deep sea](#). Ocean Sciences Meeting 2024. ED43A-02. February 2024. New Orleans.

Huber J, Ramirez G, Almacen O, D'Angelo T, Lauer RM, Sadeghpour S, Sutherland A, Voight JR, Zhivkova T, Orcutt B, Akiba R, Fisher AT, Lutz H, Serres M, Vasquez Fallas V, Wheat CG, Cortés J. [Characterization of \(sub\)seafloor microbial communities at octopus nurseries associated with low-temperature hydrothermal vents at La Pampa Submarina, Costa Rica](#). American Geophysical Union 2024. B54C-05. December 2024. Washington DC.

Leonor Pizarro, Laurine Mathé, Catarina Magalhães, Marisa Almeida, Beth Orcutt, Miguel Semedo (2024) Metal Impacts on Deep-sea Microbial N₂O Metabolism and Diversity. Oral presentation at the Pollutant Responses in Marine Organisms (PRIMO) conference, 26th - 29th May 2024, Nantes, France.

Naranjo-Elizondo, B. (2025, January 31). *A hidden skatepark: Discovery of a skate egg-case nursery on a Costa Rican seamount* (Poster presentation). Deep Sea Biology Symposium, Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Hong Kong.

Naranjo-Elizondo, B. (2025, January 31). *Costa Rica desconocida: A campaign for awareness and cultural integration of deep-sea environments* (Oral presentation). Deep Sea Biology Symposium – Open Session, Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Hong Kong.

Amon, D.J. (2025, January). *Thinking Deeply: Reflections on Experiences, Practices and Values in Deep-Sea Science*. 17th Deep-Sea Biology Symposium, Hong Kong.

Naranjo-Elizondo, B. (2025, May 29). *Integrating Costa Rica's deep-sea biodiversity into OBIS* (Oral presentation). Deep Ocean Observing Strategy (DOOS) 2025 Annual Meeting – Mobilising Deep Sea Data into OBIS Session, Virtual.

Cortés, J. (2025, June 2). *Costa Rica: A marine and unknown country* (Oral presentation). Université de Côte d'Azur, Nice, France.

Cortés, J. (2025, June 3). *The need for collaboration in deep-sea exploration* (Oral presentation). One Ocean Science Congress, Nice, France.

Naranjo-Elizondo, B. (2025, June 5). *Unlocking Costa Rica's deep sea: A digital platform for conservation and research* (Oral presentation). One Ocean Science Congress – Deep Sea Science, Knowledge of the Deep Ocean and Ways to Enable Its Sustainable Use: Open Session, Nice, France.

Angulo-Sibaja, A. (2025, August 15). *Ichthyological diversity in Costa Rica: From continental waters to the deep ocean* (Oral presentation). Universidad Autónoma de Morelos – XVIII Mexican Congress of Ichthyology & XI Latin American Ichthyology Symposium, Cuernavaca, Mexico.

Cortés, J. (2025, October 1). *Mar profundo: La última frontera. Deep-Sea Mining*. Organized by The Interamerican Association for the Defense of the Environment (Asociación Interamericana para la Defensa del Ambiente). Virtual.

Rodríguez-Jiménez, A., Sandoval-Gutiérrez, M. I., Sibaja-Cordero, J. A., & Cortés, J. (2025, November 5–8). *Unlocking the paleoceanographic secrets of the Eastern Tropical Pacific: A radiolarian perspective from Costa Rica* (Oral presentation). The Micropalaeontological Society Annual Conference TMS 2025 – Pisa: A Natural Kaleidoscope: Understanding the Earth System Through Microfossils, Pisa, Italy.

Masís-Marín, J. M., Gamboa, V., Sandoval-Gutiérrez, M. I., Sánchez Noguera, C., & Cortés, J. (2025, December 11). *Foraminíferos como indicadores ecológicos en sedimentos superficiales de la Pampa Submarina, Pacífico Norte de Costa Rica* (Poster presentation). XV CIMAR Symposium, Universidad de Costa Rica, Costa Rica.

Ramírez-Quesada, J., Gamboa-Sojo, V., Sandoval-Gutiérrez, M. I., & Cortés-Núñez, J. (2025, December 11). *Alto nivel de preservación de microfósiles de océano profundo, Pampa Submarina (Pacífico, Costa Rica)* (Poster presentation). XV CIMAR Symposium, Universidad de Costa Rica, Costa Rica.

Rodríguez-Jiménez, A., Sandoval Gutiérrez, M. I., Sibaja Cordero, J., & Cortés Núñez, J. (2025, December 11). *Radiolarios Polycystina de la Pampa Submarina (Pacífico, Costa Rica): Una perspectiva oceanográfica para el Pacífico Tropical Oriental* (Poster presentation). XV CIMAR Symposium, Universidad de Costa Rica, Costa Rica.

3.3 Cruise Records

- Cruise log
 - [Octopus Odyssey \(FKt230602\)](#)
 - [Octopus Odyssey \(Too\) \(FKt231202\)](#)
- ROV Dive Playlists
 - [Octopus Odyssey \(FKt230602\)](#)
 - [Octopus Odyssey \(Too\) \(FKt231202\)](#)

3.4 Media

Nombran “Pampa Submarina” a fondo oceánico en el Pacífico nacional. CR Hoy, February 1, 2024. <https://www.crhoy.com/ambiente/nombran-pampa-submarina-a-fondo-oceanico-en-el-pacifico-nacional/>

A Maine scientist helped discover 4 new species of octopus, Portland Press Herald, March 8, 2024. <https://www.pressherald.com/2024/03/08/a-maine-scientist-helped-discover-four-new-species-of-deep-sea-octopus/>

Senckenberg Gesellschaft für Naturforschung. (2025, April 3). *A deep-sea octopus is the “mollusk of the year 2025”*. Senckenberg Nature Research. <https://www.senckenberg.de/en/press-releases/a-deep-sea-octopus-is-the-mollusk-of-the-year-2025/>

Núñez Zúñiga, J. (2025, July 23). “Pampa Submarina” dio inicio al II ciclo lectivo en Nicoya. UNA Comunica. <https://www.unacomunica.una.ac.cr/index.php/julio-2025/6229-pampa-submarina-dio-inicio-al-ii-ciclo-lectivo-en-nicoya>

Barboza, R. (2025, July 28). *U.N.A inicia el II ciclo 2025 con lección inaugural sobre la Pampa Submarina*. Municipalidad de Nicoya. <https://nicoya.go.cr/noticia/365/una-inicia-el-ii-ciclo-2025-con-leccion-inaugural-sobre-la-pampa-submarina>

Guananoticias. (2025, July 28). *UNA inicia II ciclo 2025 con lección inaugural sobre la “Pampa Submarina”*. <https://guananoticias.com/comunales/una-inicia-ii-ciclo-2025-con-leccion-inaugural-sobre-la-pampa-submarina/>

La Voz de Galicia. (2025, November 14). *Las aguas de Galicia, Indonesia y Costa Rica llegan a la Semana de Cine Submarino de Vigo*. https://www.lavozdeg Galicia.es/noticia/somosmar/2025/11/14/aguas-galicia-indonesia-costa-rica-llegan-semana-cine-submarino-vigo/0003_202511V14C69917.htm

Metropolitano Gal. (2025, November 13). *La Semana de Cine Submarino de la UVigo ofrece más de una decena de proyecciones gratis en la ciudad*. <https://metropolitano.gal/que-hacer/la-semana-de-cine-submarino-de-la-uvigo-ofrece-mas-de-una-decena-de-proyecciones-gratis-en-la-ciudad/>

La Voz de Galicia. (2025, November 20). *Concluye la Semana de Cine Submarino con proyecciones de Galicia y Costa Rica*. https://www.lavozdeg Galicia.es/noticia/vigo/2025/11/20/cine-submarino-gallego/0003_202511V20C6999.htm

<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/22d8d3e84b5b490db4939cc43a30bd99>

XXXIII Semana de Cine Submarino, Universidad de Vigo, 20 November 2025, Vigo, Spain. <https://www.uvigo.gal/es/campus/cultura/cine/semana-cine-submarino-universidade-vigo>

3.5 Community Outreach

Droge M, [Beyond Midnight installation](#), Bates College, Lewiston, Maine, USA. December 2023 - January 2024. News media coverage here: <https://picturestories.bates.edu/all-lit-up> and here

<https://thebatesstudent.com/25239/arts-leisure/coram-deep-sea-exhibit-astonishes-in-its-deep-dive-into-new-ocean-science/>

Orcutt B. Bigelow Laboratory Presents: Exploring the Depths. The Music Hall, Portsmouth, NH, October 8, 2024. <https://www.themusichall.org/events/bigelow-labs/>

Cortés J. Pampa Submarina. Congreso de Integración de Saberes para un Océano Sostenible (CISOS 2024) in collaboration with Immersed in Change high-level UNOC3 stakeholder meeting, San José, Costa Rica, June 2024. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2QS4HjQpkq4>

Voight J. Unseen Oceans exhibit at the Field Museum, Chicago, IL, USA. 253,881 visitors.

Voight J. Changing Face of Science exhibit at the Field Museum, Chicago, IL, USA, 2/16/2024-2/23/2025. Attendance to date 130,344.

Sandoval-Gutiérrez, M., & Naranjo-Elizondo, B. (2025, January 30). *Nuestro océano: Biodiverso y profundo* (Public presentation). Virtual – LEGO Robotics Competition.

Vásquez, F. (2025, January 30). *Océano profundo* (Public presentation). Virtual – LEGO Robotics Competition.

Chacón, L. (2025, January 31). *Revelando los equinodermos de las profundidades: Un viaje a través de expediciones pasadas y recientes en Costa Rica* (Public presentation). Virtual talk organized by SOA Costa Rica.

Expedición Fotográfica Costa Rica Desconocida [Costa Rica Desconocida Photographic Expedition]. (2025, April–May). Imagery exhibition. School of Biology, Universidad de Costa Rica, San Pedro, San José, Costa Rica. A curated selection of images showcasing deep-sea biodiversity was presented, offering visitors an insight into Costa Rica’s oceanic heritage. Each exhibition had an approximate duration of 30 days. Images and accompanying texts are available at <https://costaricadesconocida.com/language/en/recursos/muestra-fotografica/>. Prints by Michel Droge were also exhibited, along with videos edited by Schmidt Ocean Institute.

Cortés, J. (2025, April 22). *Regiones profundas del océano* (Public presentation). University Week, School of Biology, Universidad de Costa Rica, San José, Costa Rica.

Expedición Fotográfica Costa Rica Desconocida acompañada de especímenes [Costa Rica Desconocida Photographic Expedition accompanied by a museum specimen display]. (2025, May–June). Exhibition. Library of the Tacaes Campus, Universidad de Costa Rica, Grecia, Alajuela, Costa Rica.

Vásquez, F. (2025, May 2). Interview for news capsule “Estamos en el trópico: ¡El molusco del año es tico!”. Conducted by Mario Fernández, Quince UCR.

Angulo Sibaja, A. (2025, May 26). *VII Semana de la diversidad lingüística de Costa Rica: Lenguaje, entorno natural y cultura* (Public presentation). Faculty of Letters & School of Biology, Universidad de Costa Rica, San José, Costa Rica.

Expedición Fotográfica Costa Rica Desconocida accompanied by a specimen display [Costa Rica Desconocida Photographic Expedition accompanied by a museum specimen display]. (2025, June). Imagery and science exhibition. Arturo Agüero Chávez Library, Universidad de Costa Rica, Sede Occidente, San Ramón, Costa Rica.

Salas-Moya, C. (2025, June 5). *Nuestro océano: Biodiverso y profundo* (Public presentation). Library of the Tacaes Campus, Universidad de Costa Rica, Grecia, Costa Rica.

Cortés, J. (2025, June 10). *Advancing deep-sea research for conservation in the Eastern Tropical Pacific Seascape – Costa Rica* (Public presentation). Costa Rica Pavilion at The Whale, Green Zone – United Nations Ocean Conference 3, Nice, France.

Cortés, J., Naranjo-Elizondo, B., Guilhon, M., & Miller, A. (2025, June 10). *Advancement of deep-sea science in Costa Rica with Schmidt Ocean Institute* (Panel discussion). United Nations Ocean Conference 3 – Side Event, Green Zone (La Baleine), Nice, France.

Sandoval-Gutiérrez, M., & Sánchez-Noguera, C. (2025, June 12). *Oceans workshop* (Workshop). Lycée Franco-Costaricien, La Unión, Cartago, Costa Rica.

Breedy, O. (2025, June 26). Interview for news capsule “Estamos en el trópico: Octocorales”. Conducted by Mario Fernández, Canal Quince UCR.

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